

Bidirectional alpha collapse, not forward wave increase, under N,N -DMT

A reanalysis of cortical travelling waves

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Abstract. Alamia et al. (2020) reported that N,N -dimethyltryptamine (DMT) significantly increases forward (bottom-up) cortical travelling waves, based on surrogate-normalized 2D FFT analysis. We reanalyze the same publicly available EEG dataset ($N = 12$) using the same method, supplemented by absolute power analysis. Absolute forward wave power decreases under DMT in all 12 subjects at alpha (8–13 Hz) and 11 of 12 at broadband (2–100 Hz); placebo produces no significant change in absolute power. Both forward and backward power collapse bidirectionally, with backward collapsing significantly more (2.3–5.1 percentage points, all $p \leq 0.002$, 12/12 subjects at alpha). This differential persists in within-subject percentage changes, which inherently normalize each direction to its own baseline. The apparent normalized forward “increase” arises because the surrogate baseline inherits the spectral collapse and drops faster than the forward signal. Forward dB at the maximum measured effect was not significantly above zero (Bayes factor $BF_{01} = 2.45$, Jeffreys–Zellner–Siow prior $r = \sqrt{2}/2$; Rouder et al., 2009), providing anecdotal evidence for convergence to the surrogate null rather than emergence of new directional activity. At the maximum measured effect, absolute forward and backward alpha power were statistically indistinguishable ($p = 0.27$), consistent with both directions collapsing to a common floor. The electrophysiological signature of DMT is better described as bidirectional wave power collapse with loss of detectable directional structure at alpha frequencies than as directional reorganization.

1 Introduction

Cortical travelling waves—spatially organized oscillatory patterns that propagate across the cortical surface—have emerged as a candidate mechanism for hierarchical information flow in the brain. Alamia and VanRullen (2019) developed a 2D fast Fourier transform (FFT) method for quantifying the balance of forward (posterior-to-anterior, putatively bottom-up) and backward (anterior-to-posterior, putatively top-down) wave propagation from scalp electroencephalography (EEG), demonstrating that resting alpha oscillations travel predominantly backward while visual stimulation shifts the balance toward forward propagation. Within the predictive coding framework, backward waves have been interpreted as carrying top-down predictions and forward waves as carrying bottom-up prediction errors (Bastos et al., 2012; Alamia & VanRullen, 2019).

Applying this method to EEG recorded during intravenous N,N -dimethyltryptamine (DMT)

administration, Alamia, Timmermann, and colleagues (2020) reported that DMT significantly increases forward travelling wave power while decreasing backward wave power, based on the surrogate-normalized dB metric. The finding was interpreted as electrophysiological evidence for enhanced bottom-up sensory processing under psychedelics, consistent with the relaxed beliefs under psychedelics (REBUS) model (Carhart-Harris & Friston, 2019), which proposes that serotonergic psychedelics reduce the precision weighting of top-down priors. The result has been cited over 50 times (Google Scholar, March 2026) and was reproduced by the same group using simultaneous EEG-fMRI (Timmermann et al., 2023), using the same surrogate-normalization procedure.

The 2D FFT method quantifies wave power relative to a surrogate distribution generated by randomly permuting the electrode ordering in the data matrix, which destroys spatial propagation structure while preserving temporal spectral content (Alamia & VanRullen, 2019; Pang et al., 2020). The resulting dB measure isolates directional wave power above what spectral content alone would produce. This normalization is standard in the travelling wave literature and appropriate for comparing directional structure across conditions with similar spectral properties.

However, DMT produces a dramatic collapse of alpha-band power—approximately 65–89% in the Timmermann dataset. Under such extreme spectral collapse, the surrogate baseline inherits the same power reduction, and the normalized metric can shift in the absence of any new directional activity. If both forward and backward wave power collapse but at slightly different rates, the dB ratio will change even though absolute power decreased in both directions. Whether the reported “forward increase” reflects genuine directional reorganization or the mathematical behavior of the normalized metric under bidirectional spectral collapse has not been examined.

Here we reanalyze the publicly available Timmermann DMT EEG dataset using Alamia’s 2D FFT method, ported from the original MATLAB code and verified line-by-line, supplemented by an absolute power analysis that directly tests whether forward wave power increases, decreases, or remains unchanged under DMT and placebo.

2 Methods

2.1 Data

We analyzed the publicly available preprocessed EEG dataset from Timmermann et al. (2019), accessed via the Open Science Framework (Alamia et al., 2020, OSF repository). Data were preprocessed as described in Timmermann et al. (2019), including bandpass filtering and artifact rejection; we used the pre-extracted condition windows without additional preprocessing. The publicly available dataset contains 12 subjects; one participant was excluded due to excessive movement artifacts (Timmermann et al., 2019). Alamia et al. (2020) report $N = 13$ in their Methods and Discussion but $N = 12$ in their correlation analyses, consistent with the deposited data. All subjects received intravenous DMT (doses: 7–20 mg) and placebo in a fixed-

order, single-blind, within-subject design (placebo first, DMT second). EEG was recorded from 32 channels (Brainproducts EasycapMR 32) at 1000 Hz; the deposited data contain six midline channels, of which Alamia et al. (2020) selected the first five (Oz, POz, Pz, Cz, FCz) for the travelling wave analysis. Four time windows were pre-extracted per session: C1 (pre-injection baseline, approximately 60–370 s), C2 (early effect, approximately 530–1000 s), C3 (mid-recovery, approximately 940–1350 s), and C4 (late recovery, approximately 1250–1720 s). A variable gap between C1 and C2 (mean approximately four minutes, range two to seven minutes across subjects), during and immediately following injection, was excluded by the original authors to avoid injection-related artifacts; C2 therefore represents the early drug effect rather than the absolute pharmacological maximum. Electrode ordering (posterior-to-anterior) was verified by confirming a monotonic alpha power gradient across electrodes (Pearson $r = -0.91$ between electrode index and mean 8–13 Hz power at C1 baseline across all subjects).

2.2 Travelling wave analysis

We implemented the 2D FFT travelling wave decomposition following Alamia and VanRullen (2019), verified line-by-line against the original MATLAB code (OSF repository). One-second sliding windows (50% overlap) were extracted from the five-electrode array. The 2D FFT was computed for each window, yielding a two-dimensional magnitude spectrum with temporal frequency on one axis and spatial frequency (across the electrode array) on the other. Forward (posterior-to-anterior) wave power was defined as the maximum value in the negative spatial frequency, positive temporal frequency quadrant; backward (anterior-to-posterior) wave power as the maximum in the positive spatial frequency, positive temporal frequency quadrant (`simmetryFlag = 0` in Alamia’s code). Because the electrode array consists of exactly five channels, the total number of possible spatial permutations is $5! = 120$. Rather than approximating the surrogate distribution via random sampling (Alamia et al., 2020, used 100 random permutations), we computed the exact surrogate baseline by evaluating all 120 permutations for each window, eliminating stochastic sampling noise from the normalization. Wave power was expressed in dB relative to the mean of this exact surrogate distribution.

2.3 Absolute power analysis

To disambiguate whether the normalized forward dB increase reflects new directional activity or bidirectional collapse, we extracted the raw (non-normalized) forward and backward 2D FFT magnitude values from the same sliding windows. We computed absolute values under four conditions crossing frequency range (alpha: 8–13 Hz; broadband: 2–100 Hz) with aggregation method (peak: maximum in the quadrant, matching Alamia’s method; sum: total power in the quadrant). For each subject, we computed the percentage change in absolute forward and backward power from C1 to C2 and counted the number of subjects showing an absolute forward increase. The same analysis was applied to the placebo condition to test drug specificity.

2.4 Differential collapse test

To test whether backward wave power collapses significantly more than forward, we computed within-subject percentage changes for each direction ($(C2_i - C1_i)/C1_i$ per subject) and performed paired t -tests on the within-subject difference (backward change% minus forward change%), supplemented by Wilcoxon signed-rank tests. We note that Table 1 reports percentage changes of the group means to illustrate the macro-level collapse, while statistical tests evaluate the mean of these within-subject percentage changes, as the ratio of group means and the mean of within-subject ratios need not be equal. We additionally computed a drug-specific contrast by subtracting each subject’s placebo change from their DMT change.

2.5 Subjective correlation inheritance test

Alamia et al. (2020) reported strong correlations between forward wave dB and subjective intensity ratings ($r = 0.96$ across time points averaged over subjects). To test whether this correlation is substantially inherited from overall alpha collapse, we computed per-subject total alpha power change (sum of absolute forward and backward alpha power, C2 minus C1, expressed as percentage change) and correlated this with per-subject change in forward dB (C2 minus C1). We note that our test examines between-subject covariance in the C1-to-C2 transition, which is related to but distinct from Alamia et al.’s across-timepoint correlation.

2.6 Additional analyses

To test whether forward dB at C2 significantly exceeded the surrogate null (zero), we performed a one-sample t -test supplemented by a Bayes factor (BF_{01}) computed using the Jeffreys–Zellner–Siow (JZS) prior on effect size (Rouder et al., 2009) with scale $r = \sqrt{2}/2$, and assessed robustness across prior widths $r = 0.5$ – 1.0 . To test whether directional asymmetry persisted at C2, we compared absolute forward versus backward power using paired t -tests at each time point. Exploratory sub-band analyses repeated the absolute power comparison for delta (2–4 Hz), theta (4–8 Hz), and beta (13–30 Hz). Recovery of the backward-dominant asymmetry was assessed by tracking the BW/FW ratio across C2–C4.

3 Results

3.1 Replication of the normalized finding

Our surrogate-normalized analysis reproduces the pattern reported by Alamia et al. (2020). Under DMT, forward wave dB increases from C1 to C2 (alpha: +0.33 dB, paired t -test, $t(11) = 5.46$, $p = 0.0002$) while backward wave dB decreases (alpha: –0.20 dB, $t(11) = 6.43$, $p < 0.0001$). Under placebo, forward dB shows a small decrease ($t(11) = -2.22$, $p = 0.048$) in the opposite direction from DMT; backward dB does not change significantly ($p = 0.086$). The qualitative pattern—forward dB increase and backward dB decrease under DMT, absent or reversed under placebo—matches the original report.

3.2 Absolute power: bidirectional collapse under DMT, not placebo

In contrast to the normalized metric, absolute forward wave power *decreases* under DMT in all or nearly all subjects across all four analysis conditions (Table 1; Figure 1A). Under placebo, forward power shows no significant change, with approximately one-third of subjects showing increases and two-thirds showing decreases—consistent with random fluctuation around baseline.

Table 1: Absolute power changes from C1 to C2. Mean percentage change across subjects; pp = percentage points; d = Cohen’s d (paired) for the forward collapse. Differential represents the mean of within-subject differences, which may differ from the difference of group means (e.g., the placebo alpha differential of +3.2 pp \neq $(-2.3) - (-2.8) = +0.5$ pp; see Section 2.4).

Condition		N FW incr.	FW change	BW change	Diff.	FW d
Alpha, peak	DMT	0/12	-64.9%	-68.8%	-3.7 pp	-1.18
	PLA	4/12	-2.8% ($p = 0.73$)	-2.3% ($p = 0.76$)	+3.2 pp ($p = 0.22$)	—
Broadband, peak	DMT	1/12	-54.7%	-60.9%	-5.1 pp	-1.37
	PLA	3/12	-6.4% ($p = 0.35$)	-5.8% ($p = 0.36$)	+2.3 pp ($p = 0.24$)	—

DMT forward alpha collapse: $t(11) = 4.10$, $p = 0.002$. Placebo forward alpha: $t(11) = 0.35$, $p = 0.73$. Drug-specific forward alpha decrease (DMT change minus placebo change): $t(11) = -3.46$, $p = 0.005$, with 11/12 subjects showing greater forward collapse under DMT than placebo. Results under summed-power aggregation are consistent (alpha sum: 0/12 DMT forward increased; broadband sum: 0/12 DMT forward increased).

The absolute forward power decrease is not confined to alpha. Exploratory sub-band analysis shows forward collapse under DMT in delta (-22.6% , $p = 0.014$, 2/12 increased), theta (-35.2% , $p = 0.003$, 1/12), and beta (-29.1% , $p = 0.003$, 0/12); theta and beta survive Bonferroni correction for four bands (threshold $p = 0.0125$), delta does not. The surrogate-normalized forward dB increases in all four bands despite these absolute decreases, confirming that the ambiguity of the normalized metric under spectral collapse is not confined to alpha. Notably, forward dB at C2 remains significantly above zero in delta ($p = 0.005$) and theta ($p < 0.001$) but not in alpha ($p = 0.38$; Section 3.3), indicating that alpha is the band in which directional structure is most completely lost. We note that Timmermann et al. (2019) reported transient increases in delta and theta *temporal* power at the subjective peak (minutes 2–3 post-injection); the C2 window used here and in Alamia et al. (2020) captures the broader post-injection period where spectral power is generally suppressed, and the 2D FFT measures spatially coherent propagating power rather than total temporal power.

3.3 The normalized metric under bidirectional collapse

The mechanism producing the normalized forward “increase” is transparent (Figure 1). At C1, mean forward alpha power (5,371 a.u.) is below the surrogate baseline (5,775 a.u.), yielding a negative forward dB (-0.25). This indicates that at rest, forward alpha carries *less* directional structure than expected from spectral content alone—consistent with the well-established

backward dominance of resting alpha (Alamia & VanRullen, 2019). At C2 under DMT, forward alpha power (1,888 a.u.) is essentially equal to the surrogate baseline (1,883 a.u.), yielding a near-zero forward dB (+0.08). The forward dB shift from -0.25 to $+0.08$ occurs because the surrogate baseline collapsed slightly faster (-67.4%) than the real forward signal (-64.9%), not because new forward-propagating activity emerged. The surrogate collapse rate (-67.4%) falls between the forward (-64.9%) and backward (-68.8%) rates, as expected: because the surrogate is generated by randomly permuting electrode order, its spectral power is a non-directional spatial average of the real forward and backward signals, and its collapse rate is therefore expected to fall between the two. Under these conditions, the normalized forward dB ($10 \log_{10}[\text{FW}/\text{surrogate}]$) must increase whenever backward power collapses more than forward, regardless of whether any new forward activity is generated.

This does not mean the surrogate-normalized metric is uninformative. The dB measure was designed to isolate directional structure above spectral content (Alamia & VanRullen, 2019), and the shift in the forward-backward dB balance does capture a real asymmetry: the forward signal retained slightly more directional structure relative to its spectral baseline than the backward signal did. However, forward dB at C2 is not significantly above zero (one-sample $t(11) = 0.91, p = 0.38$; $\text{BF}_{01} = 2.45$, JZS prior $r = \sqrt{2}/2$; robust across prior widths: $\text{BF}_{01} = 1.97\text{--}3.17$ for $r = 0.5\text{--}1.0$), providing anecdotal evidence that the forward signal converged to the surrogate null distribution rather than exceeding it.¹ The normalized metric alone cannot distinguish between “new forward activity emerged” and “bidirectional collapse erased a pre-existing backward asymmetry.” The absolute power analysis disambiguates in favor of the latter.

3.4 Backward collapse is significantly greater

Despite the small magnitude of the differential (2.3–5.1 percentage points against a background of 55–69% bidirectional collapse), paired tests confirm that backward wave power collapses significantly more than forward wave power under DMT across all four conditions (Table 2; Figure 1C). This differential is absent under placebo (all $p > 0.2$).

Table 2: Paired tests on within-subject differential collapse (backward minus forward percentage change), $df = 11$. Cohen’s d reported for alpha peak (primary analysis).

Condition	N BW > FW	Mean diff	95% CI	p	d
Alpha, peak	12/12	-3.7 pp	$[-4.9, -2.5]$	< 0.0001	-1.95
Alpha, sum	12/12	-2.5 pp	$[-3.3, -1.6]$	0.0001	—
Broadband, peak	12/12	-5.1 pp	$[-6.8, -3.4]$	< 0.0001	—
Broadband, sum	11/12	-2.3 pp	$[-3.5, -1.0]$	0.002	—

All four p -values survive Bonferroni correction for four comparisons (threshold: 0.0125). Wilcoxon signed-rank tests yield consistent results (all $p < 0.005$). The backward excess is unanimous at

¹Mean dB values reflect the average of per-window log transformations, which differs slightly from the log of the grand mean power values reported above (Jensen’s inequality).

alpha (12/12) and near-unanimous at broadband (11/12).

The within-subject percentage changes—which inherently normalize each direction to its own baseline—confirm the differential: mean backward collapse (−58.1%) exceeds mean forward collapse (−54.4%) in 12/12 subjects at alpha (paired $t(11) = -6.75, p < 0.0001$; Wilcoxon $p = 0.0005$) and 12/12 at broadband ($t(11) = -6.61, p < 0.0001$). The backward excess is therefore not driven by outliers with large baseline asymmetries, though the additive noise-floor confound discussed in Section 4.2 is not addressed by this test.

3.5 Directional structure is no longer detectable at C2

At baseline (C1), backward alpha power significantly exceeds forward (BW = 6,593, FW = 5,371; paired $t(11) = -3.00, p = 0.012, d = -0.87$; 11/12 subjects BW > FW), confirming the expected resting backward dominance. Under placebo at C2, this asymmetry is preserved ($t(11) = -3.42, p = 0.006, d = -0.99$). Under DMT at C2, however, forward and backward alpha power are statistically indistinguishable (FW = 1,888, BW = 2,056; $t(11) = -1.16, p = 0.27, d = -0.34$; $BF_{01} = 2.00$, JZS prior $r = \sqrt{2}/2$; 4/12 subjects FW > BW). The broadband result is even clearer ($t(11) = -0.70, p = 0.50, d = -0.20$; 8/12 subjects FW > BW—effectively random). Any residual directional asymmetry under DMT cannot be statistically distinguished from a common noise floor at this sample size, with both directions collapsing toward a shared level. The 2.3–5.1 percentage point differential (Section 3.4) is consistent with this convergence: a signal starting at higher absolute amplitude (backward) necessarily shows a larger percentage drop when both signals converge to the same level.

3.6 Time course and recovery

The full C1–C4 trajectory under DMT shows collapse at C2, partial recovery at C3, and near-complete recovery at C4 (Table 3). Placebo shows minimal drift across all time windows, confirming the collapse is pharmacologically driven.

Table 3: Mean absolute forward wave power (alpha, peak) across conditions (a.u. from 2D FFT magnitude spectrum).

	C1 (Pre)	C2 (Early effect)	C3 (Mid-recovery)	C4 (Late recovery)
DMT	5,371	1,888	3,222	4,974
PLA	5,346	5,198	4,715	4,788

DMT forward power recovers to approximately 93% of baseline by C4, consistent with the known pharmacokinetic half-life of intravenous DMT. The backward-dominant asymmetry, absent at C2 (Section 3.5), recovers monotonically: the backward-forward asymmetry (BW/FW excess above unity, mean of within-subject ratios) drops to 34% of its baseline magnitude at C2, then recovers to 63% at C3 and 75% at C4, though it does not reach significance by C4 ($p = 0.055$). Under placebo, the asymmetry remains significant at all four time points (all $p < 0.03$). Directional asymmetry recovers more slowly than absolute power (75% vs. 93%

at C4), consistent with the noise-floor interpretation: when absolute values are suppressed, the BW–FW difference is proportionally harder to detect because it must exceed measurement noise that remains roughly constant regardless of signal amplitude.

3.7 Subjective correlation is partially inherited

Per-subject alpha collapse significantly predicts the change in forward dB ($r = -0.67, p = 0.018, N = 12$; 95% CI: $[-0.90, -0.16]$), explaining approximately 44% of the between-subject variance: the more severely a subject’s absolute alpha power collapsed, the higher their normalized forward dB climbed. Alpha collapse more strongly predicts backward dB change ($r = 0.84, p = 0.0007, 70\%$ of variance). These correlations are consistent with the subjective intensity associations reported by Alamia et al. (2020) being partially attributable to overall alpha power reduction, though the wide confidence intervals at this sample size preclude strong conclusions about the degree of inheritance.

Figure 1: **Bidirectional alpha collapse under DMT.** (A) Absolute alpha-band power in the forward, surrogate, and backward 2D FFT quadrants at C1 (pre-injection) and C2 (early DMT effect). All three signals collapse; the surrogate falls between forward and backward as expected from its construction as a non-directional spatial average. (B) The same data expressed as surrogate-normalized dB. Forward dB appears to “increase” because the surrogate baseline drops faster than the forward signal. Backward dB decreases. Error bars: ± 1 SEM. (C) Per-subject percentage collapse in forward (x -axis) vs. backward (y -axis) alpha power. All 12 subjects fall below the unity line, indicating backward power collapses more than forward in every subject.

4 Discussion

4.1 Bidirectional collapse, not directional reorganization

The central finding is that absolute forward travelling wave power decreases under DMT in all 12 subjects at alpha and in 11 or 12 at broadband, while placebo produces no signifi-

cant change in absolute power. Both directions of wave propagation collapse bidirectionally, with backward power collapsing slightly but significantly more. We note that Alamia et al. (2020) reported a surrogate-normalized metric, not an absolute power claim; the dB increase they described is a real property of the normalized data. However, the normalized metric alone cannot distinguish between the generation of new forward-propagating activity and the asymmetric collapse of pre-existing bidirectional activity. The absolute power analysis disambiguates in favor of the latter interpretation. We note that Alamia et al. (2020) themselves reported absolute power decreases in their Figure 2C, describing the result as “an overall decrease in oscillatory power following DMT injection.” The present analysis examines what this collapse implies for the interpretation of the normalized metric.

The distinction matters for theoretical interpretation. “Enhanced bottom-up processing” (the language implied by “forward increase”) suggests new ascending activity emerges under DMT. “Bidirectional collapse with loss of detectable directional structure” (Section 3.5) suggests existing directional architecture is no longer detectable, with the apparent backward excess attributable to convergence arithmetic. These descriptions carry different mechanistic implications, even though both are consistent with the normalized dB data.

4.2 Implications for the predictive coding interpretation

The REBUS model (Carhart-Harris & Friston, 2019) proposes that psychedelics reduce the precision weighting of top-down priors; Alamia et al. (2020) interpreted their forward dB increase as evidence for “increased bottom-up signal passing” consistent with this framework. The critical point is that the data do not support the claim that bottom-up wave power is *enhanced* under DMT—forward alpha power decreased in every subject, it did not increase. Whatever the correct interpretation of the backward excess, the “forward increase” that anchored the electrophysiological case for enhanced ascending processing does not survive absolute power analysis. We note that a REBUS proponent could accept the bidirectional collapse interpretation and still argue that the differential is consistent with reduced top-down precision. The convergence arithmetic analysis (below) suggests this differential requires no pathway-specific explanation, but even setting that aside, our point is narrower: the specific claim that forward (bottom-up) wave power *increases* under DMT is not supported by the absolute data.

The observed backward excess (Table 2; Figure 1C) is consistent with reduced top-down precision within the REBUS framework, since the alpha oscillations interpreted as carrying feedback predictions (Alamia & VanRullen, 2019; Bastos et al., 2012) collapse slightly more than those interpreted as carrying feedforward errors. However, we caution against building strong theoretical claims on this differential. The mapping from backward travelling waves to top-down predictions, though supported by computational modelling (Alamia & VanRullen, 2019; Schwenk & Alamia, 2025) and consistent with laminar recordings in non-human primates (Bastos et al., 2012), remains an interpretation of the scalp-level data. More importantly, the differential (2.3–5.1 percentage points) may partly reflect a noise-floor confound: during massive alpha desynchronization, both forward and backward signals converge toward a

shared aperiodic background (the $1/f$ spectral floor, which itself flattens under psychedelics; Timmermann et al., 2019). Because backward alpha starts at higher absolute amplitude, converging onto the same noise floor produces a slightly larger percentage drop than for the lower-amplitude forward signal.² The within-subject percentage changes (Section 3.4) inherently normalize each direction to its own baseline, and the backward excess persists, but this does not address the additive noise-floor confound. Consistent with this interpretation, absolute forward and backward alpha power are statistically indistinguishable at C2 ($p = 0.27$, $d = -0.34$; Section 3.5), whereas at baseline they differ significantly ($p = 0.012$, $d = -0.87$) and under placebo the asymmetry is preserved ($p = 0.006$). The convergence to a common level is the expected outcome if both signals collapsed toward a shared noise floor, regardless of starting amplitude. To test this directly, we estimated a per-subject convergence floor as the mean of absolute forward and backward power at C2, then computed the differential that pure convergence arithmetic would predict given each subject’s baseline amplitudes. The predicted backward excess (5.74 pp) exceeds the observed backward excess (3.71 pp); the two are not significantly different (paired $t(11) = -1.03$, $p = 0.33$; Wilcoxon $p = 0.23$; $BF_{01} = 2.24$, JZS prior $r = \sqrt{2}/2$). The backward excess is consistent with starting-amplitude convergence, and no pathway-specific vulnerability is required by the data. Indeed, the observed backward excess (3.71 pp) is *smaller* than the convergence prediction (5.74 pp), suggesting if anything that backward waves were slightly more resilient than starting amplitudes alone would predict—the opposite of selective top-down vulnerability. We note that this test is not fully independent, since the convergence floor is estimated from the same C2 data used to compute the observed differential; the test confirms arithmetic plausibility rather than providing an independent causal demonstration. The drug-specificity of the differential (absent under placebo) reflects the fact that DMT produces the collapse and placebo does not, rather than indicating directional selectivity.

We further note that the Alamia travelling wave framework has been validated independently of the DMT finding, including in schizophrenia (Alamia et al., 2025; $N = 146$ patients), meditation (Bailey et al., 2025; $N = 97$), and working memory (Zeng et al., 2024). Our reanalysis addresses the interpretation of the DMT-specific result, not the broader framework.

4.3 Related findings

Blackburne et al. (2025) independently reported that cortical travelling waves cease travelling in canonical directions under 5-MeO-DMT ($N = 29$), a finding broadly consistent with the bidirectional collapse reported here, though the two compounds differ substantially in receptor pharmacology and phenomenology.

4.4 Subjective correlations

The strong correlation between forward wave dB and subjective intensity reported by Alamia et al. (2020, $r = 0.96$ across time) is partially accounted for by overall alpha collapse (44%

²A toy example illustrates the arithmetic: if backward power starts at 100 and forward at 50, and both collapse to a common floor of 10, the percentage drops are 90% and 80% respectively—a 10 percentage point “preferential backward loss” arising from pure convergence.

of between-subject variance in the C1-to-C2 transition; 95% CI on r : $[-0.90, -0.16]$). Because alpha power is among the strongest EEG correlates of subjective psychedelic intensity (Timmermann et al., 2019), any metric that covaries with alpha collapse will inherit this correlation to some degree. The remaining variance may reflect genuine directional structure in residual activity, or other spectral features that track the pharmacological time course. We emphasize that our between-subject analysis is not directly comparable to Alamia et al.'s across-timepoint correlation, and the question of whether forward dB carries unique predictive information beyond alpha power warrants dedicated investigation.

4.5 Limitations

This reanalysis uses the same dataset ($N = 12$) and electrode montage (five midline channels) as the original study. The sample size provides adequate power for the mean bidirectional collapse effect but limited precision for the differential (95% CI: $[-4.9, -2.5]$ percentage points for alpha peak). The posterior-weighted montage (three of five electrodes posterior to Cz) may overrepresent occipital alpha generators, and five midline electrodes constitute very poor spatial resolution for a 2D FFT; when alpha collapses, local noise fluctuations across these few points may dominate the spatial spectrum. Reference sensitivity was not characterized; with only five channels, average referencing is heavily influenced by dominant generators, and the effects of alternative referencing schemes on the 2D FFT directional measures are unknown. We have not applied the absolute power analysis to the Timmermann et al. (2023) EEG-fMRI dataset, which reproduced the normalized forward increase; whether the bidirectional collapse pattern generalizes to that independent recording remains an open question. Importantly, the C2 window does not capture the true pharmacological peak: an approximately three-minute period during and immediately following injection was excluded by the original authors, and C2 represents early drug effect rather than maximum intensity. The bidirectional collapse at C2 is therefore a conservative estimate; the true peak may show even greater power suppression and more complete loss of directional structure, though this cannot be confirmed from available data. Finally, it has been argued that EEG-level travelling waves may reflect sequential activation of discrete cortical modules rather than genuine wave propagation (Orsher et al., 2024), a caveat that applies equally to the original finding and to the present reanalysis.

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Data availability

The EEG dataset analyzed is publicly available in the Open Science Framework repository accompanying Alamia et al. (2020): <https://osf.io/wujgp/>.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no competing interests.

Funding

The author received no external funding for this work.